

SOME ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE REGIONAL JUSTICE BODIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550984>

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 171 dated March 19, 2025 “On measures for organizing the activities of the Institute for retraining and advanced training of legal personnel under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, one of the main tasks of the Institute is to develop scientifically based proposals for the scientific, methodological and consultative support of the activities of justice bodies and institutions, the provision of legal services, forensic examination, archival work and office work sphere, as well as to further improve them by analyzing their areas of activity.

For this purpose, it is determined that the Institute will carry out work on developing proposals and relevant scientific and methodological manuals to improve the effectiveness of the activities of justice bodies and institutions, in particular, their territorial departments.

This thesis discusses some issues related to the organization and improvement of the activities of territorial departments of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Information about the history of the ministry is provided in various open sources, in particular on its official website (<https://adliya.uz/inner-page/vazirlik-tarixi>), and the activities of the ministry have gradually improved over the years and expanded their areas of activity.

As is known, since 2018, justice bodies have been operating in a 3-tier system, i.e. at the republican, regional and district levels (republic - region - district (city)). It was on April 13, 2018 that district (city) justice departments were established.

The activities of the Ministry and its organizations are regulated by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-3666 dated April 13, 2018 and a number of other documents.

It should be noted that the Ministry of Justice occupies a leading position among the ministries, committees and other agencies of the republic, is one of

the ministries that has been performing its tasks and functions at a high level and achieving positive results.

Nevertheless, in today's fast-paced world, it is natural to conduct research aimed at improving the efficiency of the activities of justice bodies and institutions, identifying shortcomings in their activities and eliminating them. Of course, the Ministry of Justice and its structures in the system are constantly working to improve their activities. However, since employees of justice bodies are mainly busy with the implementation of the tasks assigned to them, current affairs, and also because it may be useful to look at the activities from the outside, it is advisable to conduct independent scientific and practical research.

According to paragraph 9 of the Regulation on the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-3666 dated April 13, 2018 (Appendix 1), **the following are the main tasks of the Ministry:**

- to pursue a unified state policy in the field of lawmaking;
- to coordinate activities on assessing the regulatory impact of regulatory legal acts and their drafts and conducting anti-corruption expertise;
- to ensure the dissemination and use of legal information;
- to carry out legal propaganda and coordinate the work of state bodies and organizations in the field of legal propaganda;
- to implement measures to ensure consistent and uniform law enforcement practice in the activities of the republican executive authorities and their territorial divisions and local state authorities, as well as to provide methodological assistance to these state bodies and citizens' self-government bodies in forming a unified law enforcement practice;
- to implement measures to legally protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens;
- to conduct studies across sectors, regions and organization and monitor the situation on the ground to ensure the timely, full and high-quality implementation of legislative acts and instructions;
- analysis and monitoring of the effectiveness of the public administration system based on advanced foreign experience and modern development trends;
- coordination, control and methodological assistance in the activities of legal services of state bodies and organizations, as well as ensuring the provision of legal services to state bodies and organizations established by legislative acts;
- ensuring the effective functioning of notaries, law firms and other structures providing legal services to individuals and legal entities;

participation in the development and implementation of measures to combat the legalization of proceeds from criminal activities, the financing of terrorism and the financing of the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction;

implementation of state policy in the field of developing the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, assistance in organizing their interaction with state bodies and organizations;

implementation of a single state policy in the field of administrative procedures;

implementation of a single state policy in the field of providing public services to individuals and legal entities;

improvement of the procedure for providing public services by eliminating unnecessary administrative procedures, as well as the development of interdepartmental electronic cooperation;

monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of the activities of state bodies and other organizations in the field of public services, including the implementation of relevant information systems, resources and databases;

developing a unified state policy in the field of intellectual property and protecting rights to inventions, trademarks, copyrights and other intellectual property objects;

legal protection of inventions, utility models, industrial designs, trademarks and other intellectual property objects;

organizing the training, retraining and advanced training of legal personnel, ensuring the implementation of fundamental and applied research in the field of jurisprudence;

developing priority areas for the development of forensic expertise, coordinating the training and advanced training of forensic experts;

analyzing the indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international ratings and indices in the political and legal sphere;

establishing and strengthening international legal cooperation, conducting legal expertise of international treaties;

ensuring the legal protection of the interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international and foreign organizations;

coordination of the activities of state bodies and organizations related to maintaining a unified electronic register of mandatory requirements in the field of entrepreneurship;

implementation of a unified state policy in the field of archival work and business administration and coordination of the work of state bodies and organizations in this area;

implementation of a unified state policy in the field of personal data and control and coordination of the activities of state bodies and organizations in the field of working with personal data.

They were established in an updated form with the addition of a number of new tasks by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-80 dated May 24, 2024. Clause 10 of the Regulation lists the numerous functions of the Ministry that it performs in accordance with the 26 tasks assigned to it above.

The Ministry performs the tasks and functions assigned to it directly, as well as through justice bodies and institutions, including territorial justice departments.

In accordance with Clause 8 of the above-mentioned Regulation on the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry system includes:

- The central office of the Ministry;
- The Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city justice departments, district (city) justice departments, legal service centers, public service centers and bodies of registration of civil status documents;
- “Uzarxiv” agency, territorial departments of archival work of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city, National archive of Uzbekistan, National archive of cinematographic and photographic documents of Uzbekistan, National archive of scientific, technical and medical documents of Uzbekistan, Central state archive of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Central state archive of Tashkent city, regional, city and district state archives and their branches;
- Personalization agency;
- Republican center for forensic expertise named after Kh. Sulaymonova;
- State institution “Adolat” national legal information center”;
- State institution “Center for development of information and communication technologies in justice bodies and institutions”;
- State institution “Center for intellectual property”;
- State notary offices and archives;
- Institute for retraining and advanced training of legal personnel;
- Institute for analysis and assessment of the impact of legislation;
- Tashkent state university of law and its academic lyceums;

- law colleges.

Territorial justice departments have a special place in this system. The central office of the Ministry, the Ministry of justice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, territorial justice departments, and district (city) justice departments are law enforcement agencies.

Territorial justice departments:

The middle-level justice bodies are the Ministry of justice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city justice departments. They include their internal departments, legal colleges, archives of bodies of registration of civil status documents, the notary archive, and district (city) justice departments in their system.

District (city) justice departments:

District (city) justice departments include their internal departments, legal service centers, public service centers, bodies of registration of civil status documents and notary offices in their system.

Territorial justice bodies assist the Ministry in implementing a unified state legal policy. Nevertheless, some negative factors can cause deficiencies in their activity. For example, according to practitioners, some of the following conditions may have a negative impact on performance:

1. Some legal service centers are assigned staff units consisting of 3 employees, and due to the large volume of work, it is physically difficult to perform them fully and qualitatively. As a result, they have to work more overtime.

2. Legal service centers receive documents for review from various state bodies and organizations. Due to the fact that many documents are not legal-technically and linguistically correct, the main working hours of the center's employees, in addition to legal examination of documents, are spent on their legal-technical and linguistic correction.

In order to eliminate these situations, the following can be given as preliminary suggestions. Incorporation of staff units responsible for legal technical and linguistic formalization of documents in the centers. Or require employees of relevant state bodies and organizations responsible for working with legal documents to have at least a secondary specialized legal education. Currently, legal colleges of the Ministry of Justice in each territorial unit are training graduates. In addition, measures can be taken to reduce the workload by automating recurring shortcomings in the future.

In general, in order to improve the efficiency of the activities of territorial justice bodies, we consider it appropriate to conduct research and analysis in the following areas and identify existing shortcomings:

- increasing human resources potential;
- considering the issue of digital transformation, the use of artificial intelligence in conducting of each function;
- improving the monitoring and evaluation system;
- relations with public;
- internal control;
- improving infrastructure.

It should be noted that the opinions expressed in this thesis are based on the existing situation and are preliminary. In order to develop further scientifically based proposals to improve the effectiveness of the activities of territorial departments and departments of justice, it will be necessary to directly study the activities of territorial departments, conduct internships in them, study foreign experience, obtain and analyze statistics, study the opinions of practitioners, etc.

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